

IMPACT OF FOLIAR FERTILIZATION OF MACRO AND MICRO-NUTRIENTS ON YIELD AND QUALITY OF NAGPUR MANDARIN (*Citrus reticulata* Blanco.)D.S. Meena^{*1}, P. Bhatnagar¹, M. L. Meena² and V.S. Meena²^{*1} College of Horticulture and Forestry, Jhalawar, Agriculture University, Kota,² Agricultural Research Station, Mandor, Agriculture University, Jodhpur: dsfruitscience@gmail.com

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Abstract

A field experiment entitled "Impact of foliar fertilization of macro and micro-nutrients on yield and quality of Nagpur mandarin (*Citrus reticulata* Blanco.)" was conducted during the year 2018-19, at Instructional Farm, Department of Fruit Science, College of Horticulture and Forestry, Jhalawar. The experiment consisted of different treatments of nutrients including macro and micro-nutrients and was laid out in randomized complete block design (RCBD). Amongst the different foliar spray of nutrients. The application of ZnSO₄ 0.5 % + K₂SO₄ 1.0 % foliar application was found significantly superior in terms of yield and quality parameters such as number of fruit/tree, estimated yield (kg/tree), fruit weight, fruit length, fruit breadth, peel thickness and juice recovery percentage. Whereas, lowest rag percentage over other rest of treatment. The treatment ZnSO₄ 0.5 % + K₂SO₄ 1.0 % foliar application is most effective for the farmers of vicinity area of Jhalawar.

Keywords- Nagpur mandarin, macro nutrient, micro-nutrient, quality and yield

Introduction

Nagpur mandarin (*Citrus reticulata* Blanco.) belongs to family Rutaceae. It having shizolysigenic oil gland and particular aroma indicating flavour of particular citrus species. It is considered to be one of the most important cultivated species among citrus and is being commercially grown in specific region of the country like Nagpur mandarin in Central India, (Vikee et al., 2018. Nagpur mandarin is chiefly grown in Satpura hills (Vidarbha region) of Central India, hilly slopes of Darjeeling (West Bengal), Coorg (Karnataka) and Jhalawar (Rajasthan). In Jhalawar district of Rajasthan state, it is the major fruit crop highly acclimated under vertisols. Jhalawar district receives annual rainfall of 950 mm and black vertisols with enriched calcium carbonate is highly suitable for Nagpur mandarin cultivation. Nagpur Mandarin is one of the finest varieties in term of sugars acid blend possessing tangy taste and very popular in India as well as in world. Its fruit is big, sub-globose, weigh 110-125 g, rind medium thick, peel fairly loosely adherent, surface is also relatively smooth but dominant sometimes with expression of root stock characteristics. In a single fruit there are 10-11 segments and there are 1-2 seeds per segment. The colour of peel is pale orange and fruits have mild flavour, excellent quality, juicy pulp TSS 10-12⁰ Brix, and acidity in the range 0.50-0.70 per cent. Fully mature tree bears 125 kg fruits (Bhatnagar et al., 2015). The total production of mandarin in India is 51.01 lakh tonnes from an area of 4.28 lakh hectares with the productivity of 14.84 MT/ha, In Rajasthan state, the acreage of Nagpur mandarin is around 23,900 ha area and the production is 4.7 lac tonnes (Anon., 2018). Plant nutrients are categorized as macro and micro nutrients. Besides, nitrogen, phosphorous and potassium are also required in large amounts, however micro nutrients specially zinc, iron, copper and manganese are required in small amounts. Citrus is considered highly nutrient responsive crop and site-specific nutrient management involving combination of macro and micro nutrients is must to solve nutrient deficiencies as well as to improve nutritional quality of mandarin. In Nagpur mandarin, the role of nutrients especially potassium in enhancement of fruit quality is well known. Potassium is one of the key elements which plays an important role in determining yield and quality. Nutritional K-sprays are required to increase fruit yield as well quality attributes specially juice recovery percentage and ascorbic acid content. Potassium is needed for enzyme activation, cell division, photosynthesis, photosynthates transport and osmo-regulations (Marques et al., 2018). Potassium is responsible for many important internal and external fruit characteristics including fruit size, rind thickness and colour (Mongi and Obreza, 2003). Among essential nutrients, zinc (Zn) after nitrogen (N) is undoubtedly the most widely reported deficient nutrient in citrus orchards. In citrus, the role of zinc is performed both in term of growth and yield potential. Low level of zinc reduces fruit number per tree and reduces fruit quality. Zinc plays an important role as a co-factor of number enzymes and also involved in the production of growth regulation and chloroplast development.

Foliar application of zinc is most effective in controlling zinc deficiency (rosette formation) and improvement of vegetative growth attributes, fruit morphological attributes and internal fruit quality attributes like total soluble solid and ascorbic acid content. Zinc also plays an important role in reducing pre harvest fruit drop (Mongi and Obreza, 2003). Iron plays an important role in citrus production. It acts as a catalyst in oxidation reduction reactions. It is also involved in respiration, photosynthesis and the reduction of nitrate and sulphate. It is also a co-factor in many enzymes. Iron deficiency is common in calcareous soils. Jhalawar soil contains a high concentration of calcium carbonate and has an average pH of about 8.3. These soils may contain appreciable amounts of iron, but it exists in a form that is slightly available to plants, Iron deficiency in Nagpur mandarin plants can be induced by high phosphorus or accumulation of copper in the soil. Copper plays an important role in photosynthesis, carboxylation efficiency, pollen viability, fruit set, respiration and water use efficiency. Copper deficiency is known as 'die back', 'ammoniation' and 'exanthema'. These names are synchronously synthesized from dying back of the twigs, frequent association with excess application of nitrogen and exudates on the surface of the twigs and fruits. The first symptoms of copper deficiency are formation of unusually vigorous, large, dark green foliage with a "bowing up" of the midrib. Twigs are unusually vigorous, long, angular, soft, frequently "S" shaped and somewhat drooping type. As deficiency become severe, the twig starts to die, some of the weak twigs will bear very small, yellowish green leaves that drop quickly, leaving the entire twig defoliated. The symptoms of copper deficiencies are most pronounced in orange. Brown stained area of hardened gum on the fruit rind may precede the appearance of leaf and twig symptoms (Mongi and Obreza, 2009). Insufficient application of micro-nutrients and macro-nutrients to mandarin trees results in extreme depletion of macronutrients and micronutrients and multiple nutrient deficiencies may appear. Since mineral nutrients are major factor in maximizing quality and yield of citrus fruits. Citrus especially Nagpur mandarin is highly nutrient responsive crop both in terms of macro and micro nutrients, therefore, present investigation was being undertaken on Nagpur mandarin plants at Fruit Instructional Farm of College of Horticulture and Forestry, Jhalawar to study the foliar effect of potassium, zinc, iron and copper alone and in combination among these nutrients for fruit quality and yield enhancement of mandarin.

Materials and Methods

The experimental entitled "Impact of foliar fertilization of macro and micro-nutrients on yield and quality of Nagpur mandarin (*Citrus reticulata* Blanco.)" was conducted during the year 2018-19, at the Instructional Farm, Department of Fruit Science, College of Horticulture and Forestry, Jhalawar (Table 1). The solutions of 0.25 % ZnSO₄, 0.5 % ZnSO₄, 0.25 % CuSO₄ and 0.5 % CuSO₄ were prepared by diluting 25 g ZnSO₄, 50 g ZnSO₄, 25 g CuSO₄ and 50 g CuSO₄ in 10 liters of water for two mandarin plants and solutions were used after

neutralizing with overnight soaking in lime to avoid leaf scorching and to increase absorption. Foliar application of macro and micro-nutrients was done with battery operated hand Knapsac sprayer at gravel stage during first week of may and at marvel stage during first week of July. The solution of 0.50 % K_2SO_4 and 1.0 % K_2SO_4 were prepared by diluting 50 g K_2SO_4 and 100 g K_2SO_4 in 10 liter of water for two mandarin plants. The experiment was laid down in randomized block design with three replications. The data generated during the experimentation were subjected to statistically analysed by Panse and

Table 1 Details of treatments.

Symbol	Treatment contents	Symbol	Treatment contents
T ₁	Control	T ₁₇	ZnSO ₄ (0.50%) + CuSO ₄ (0.50%)
T ₂	ZnSO ₄ (0.25%)	T ₁₈	ZnSO ₄ (0.25%) + K ₂ SO ₄ (0.50%)
T ₃	ZnSO ₄ (0.50%)	T ₁₉	ZnSO ₄ (0.25%) + K ₂ SO ₄ (1.0%)
T ₄	FeSO ₄ (0.25%)	T ₂₀	ZnSO ₄ (0.50%) + K ₂ SO ₄ (0.50%)
T ₅	FeSO ₄ (0.50%)	T ₂₁	ZnSO ₄ (0.50%) + K ₂ SO ₄ (1.0%)
T ₆	CuSO ₄ (0.25%)	T ₂₂	FeSO ₄ (0.25%) + CuSO ₄ (0.25%)
T ₇	CuSO ₄ (0.50%)	T ₂₃	FeSO ₄ (0.25%) + CuSO ₄ (0.50%)
T ₈	K ₂ SO ₄ (0.50%)	T ₂₄	FeSO ₄ (0.50%) + CuSO ₄ (0.25%)
T ₉	K ₂ SO ₄ (1.0%)	T ₂₅	FeSO ₄ (0.50%) + CuSO ₄ (0.50%)
T ₁₀	ZnSO ₄ (0.25%) + FeSO ₄ (0.25%)	T ₂₆	FeSO ₄ (0.25%) + K ₂ SO ₄ (0.50%)
T ₁₁	ZnSO ₄ (0.25%) + FeSO ₄ (0.50%)	T ₂₇	FeSO ₄ (0.25%) + K ₂ SO ₄ (1.0%)
T ₁₂	ZnSO ₄ (0.50%) + FeSO ₄ (0.25%)	T ₂₈	FeSO ₄ (0.50%) + K ₂ SO ₄ (0.50%)
T ₁₃	ZnSO ₄ (0.50%) + FeSO ₄ (0.50%)	T ₂₉	FeSO ₄ (0.50%) + K ₂ SO ₄ (1.0%)
T ₁₄	ZnSO ₄ (0.25%) + CuSO ₄ (0.25%)	T ₃₀	CuSO ₄ (0.25%) + K ₂ SO ₄ (0.50%)
T ₁₅	ZnSO ₄ (0.25%) + CuSO ₄ (0.50%)	T ₃₁	CuSO ₄ (0.25%) + K ₂ SO ₄ (1.0%)
T ₁₆	ZnSO ₄ (0.50%) + CuSO ₄ (0.25%)	T ₃₂	CuSO ₄ (0.50%) + K ₂ SO ₄ (0.50%)
		T ₃₃	CuSO ₄ (0.50%) + K ₂ SO ₄ (1.0%)

Results and Discussions

The experiment results revealed that the significantly higher number of fruits (579.0 /tree) were recorded fruit yield/plant (96.19 kg), fruit weight (161.53 g), fruit length (6.31 cm) and breadth (7.00 cm), peel thickness (3.07 mm), juice recovery percentage (51.91 %) under T₂₁ treatment (ZnSO₄ @ 0.5 % + K₂SO₄ @ 1.0 %) which was at par with T₂₀ treatment (ZnSO₄ @ 0.5 % + K₂SO₄ @ 0.5 %) as compared to rest of the treatments. The probable reason for increase in fruit number might be reduction in fruit drop (Nijjar (1985). K application reduced fruit drop and increased number of fruits per tree in T₂₁ treatment (ZnSO₄ @ 0.5 % + K₂SO₄ @ 1.0 %). It might be due to important role played by Zinc in biosynthesis of IAA (Alloway, 2008). The present results are also supported by the finding of Ismail (1994) who found that foliar application of micro-nutrients increased yield of Valencia orange. The highest yield observed in T₂₁ treatment could be attributed to the combined role of zinc and potassium sulphate which favoured increment of chlorophyll production and photosynthesis processes and perhaps it leads to increase in terms of fruit yield up to 15 %. Foliar feeding of combined application of Zn and K might have improved the tree health. In plants well supplied with Zn and K, the osmotic potential of the phloem sap and the volume flow rate are higher than in the plants grown under low K fertility and as a result, sucrose concentration in the phloem sap is increased and due to which juice vessels gets filled with sufficient sap. The present results are in accordance with those reported by Marschner (1995) and Babu *et al.*, (2007) in Kinnow mandarin. The changes recorded in rag percent with foliar application of micro-nutrients and reveal a significant increase in juice percent and a concomitant decrease in rag percent as compare to other treatments. The minimum rag percent (8.80 %) was estimated in treatment T₂₁ (ZuSO₄ @ 0.5 % + K₂SO₄@ 0.5 %). The results of present findings are in line with the results of Babu and Yadav (2005) who reported that Zn application increase fruit weight percentage and reduced rag percentage in sweet orange.

Conclusion

On the basis of results obtained from the field experiment, it may be concluded that the foliar spray of different micro and macro-nutrients influenced the growth, yield and quality of fruits Nagpur mandarin

Sukhatme (1954). The present investigations were undertaken at Fruit Instructional Farm, College of Horticulture and Forestry, Jhalawar on eleven old plants of Nagpur mandarin planted at spacing of 6 X 6 meter under square system of planting. The total number of plants included in the experiment was 99. All the mandarin plants were selected on the basis of desired uniformity in growth and vigour and bearer. All the treatments were applied in first week of May, 2018 and first week of July, 2018. The remaining all the package of practices followed as suggested by Agriculture University, Kota.

(*Citrus reticulata* Blanco.) specially under Agro-climatic zone-V of Rajasthan *i.e.* in (Jhalawar condition). Among the different treatments, foliar fertilization of ZnSO₄ @ 0.5% + K₂SO₄ @ 1.0 % at first week of May and first week of July for 11 years old orchards was found superior over rest of the treatments.

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Table 2. Effect of foliar fertilization of nutrients on fruit yield and quality of Nagpur mandarin.

Symbol	Fruits/tree	Yield (kg/plant)	Fruit Weight (g)	Fruit length (cm)	Fruit breadth (cm)	Peel thickness (mm)	Juice recovery (%)	Rag (%)
T ₁	405.00	49.81	123.00	4.75	5.00	2.12	36.37	15.14
T ₂	463.66	62.76	135.36	5.20	5.73	2.32	41.63	21.04
T ₃	483.33	64.85	135.56	5.26	5.73	2.34	48.29	15.67
T ₄	424.00	58.43	137.86	5.26	5.84	2.34	44.33	19.52
T ₅	431.00	59.02	136.96	5.24	5.87	2.31	41.45	14.95
T ₆	427.66	58.55	136.90	5.24	5.83	2.36	47.36	14.14
T ₇	430.66	60.94	141.50	5.37	5.72	2.33	46.33	15.49
T ₈	459.00	63.11	137.46	5.43	5.90	2.38	40.96	12.17
T ₉	482.33	67.88	140.76	5.37	5.91	2.44	45.04	15.88
T ₁₀	497.33	71.09	145.26	5.51	5.51	2.45	41.63	9.02
T ₁₁	499.00	67.93	136.10	5.20	5.34	2.26	43.31	13.00
T ₁₂	505.66	68.76	136.00	5.21	5.21	2.31	46.59	15.26
T ₁₃	510.33	70.08	137.33	5.11	5.30	2.32	40.40	13.87
T ₁₄	500.00	66.78	133.56	5.12	5.11	2.32	44.24	13.30
T ₁₅	502.64	67.36	134.00	5.11	5.11	2.29	40.00	9.23
T ₁₆	501.33	74.59	148.80	5.65	5.65	2.49	44.34	17.04
T ₁₇	510.33	76.87	150.66	5.81	5.80	2.46	49.05	17.52
T ₁₈	521.00	72.03	138.30	5.21	5.21	2.37	42.45	12.83
T ₁₉	550.00	73.27	133.26	5.08	5.08	2.59	40.23	12.04
T ₂₀	570.33	78.95	138.43	5.25	5.76	2.71	48.09	16.44
T ₂₁	579.00	96.19	161.53	6.31	7.00	3.07	51.91	8.80
T ₂₂	486.66	67.69	139.10	5.31	5.93	2.35	40.66	13.87
T ₂₃	503.00	66.51	132.26	5.07	5.67	2.28	42.44	16.78
T ₂₄	507.00	69.92	137.93	5.27	5.82	2.43	39.56	16.25
T ₂₅	508.00	69.77	137.36	5.26	5.87	2.23	40.44	10.12
T ₂₆	485.33	63.56	132.03	5.03	5.65	2.27	42.91	12.00
T ₂₇	488.00	68.04	139.43	5.20	5.97	2.40	43.15	12.04
T ₂₈	492.66	69.71	141.50	5.43	5.86	2.42	41.22	10.25
T ₂₉	494.66	70.31	142.13	5.43	5.98	2.42	44.33	10.06
T ₃₀	489.00	64.66	132.26	5.08	5.58	2.26	49.75	21.48
T ₃₁	490.00	65.17	133.10	5.21	5.61	2.37	43.90	11.63
T ₃₂	491.33	66.82	141.10	5.39	5.90	2.47	47.76	12.92
T ₃₃	493.00	68.10	138.16	5.31	5.76	2.39	42.37	11.65
S.Em₊	3.96	1.93	3.95	0.82	0.13	0.18	1.49	0.97
C.D. (p=0.05)	11.19	5.47	11.16	2.32	0.37	0.52	4.21	2.76